

OPTIMIZATION OF PATCHED REPAIR FOR CFRP LAMINATES

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This study proposes a design tool for optimizing external patched repairs. Experimental observations associated with finite element analysis have shown that measured failure load varies in the same tendency as that of calculated damage initiation as a function of different repair parameters. An optimal strength ratio R^* has been defined, and then a parameter K has been proposed for the purpose of patched repair optimization.

Keywords: Patched repair, Optimization of composite structure, Finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

The increased use of composite structures poses questions about the repair of damaged structures. In many cases, the cost of complex composite structures is too high to systematically replace damaged ones. A local patched-repair can be considered as a good solution for economical and mechanical reasons [1]. In order to guarantee the load transmission, the process of local repair used in industry is actually quite complicated to realize: a great amount of material in the damage area will be firstly removed associated with a very low scarf angle, and then the patches need to be bonded layer by layer. Another more practical method of local repair is also developed using external bonded patches. Up to now, a lot of attention has been paid on the patch conception concerning the geometry [2, 3], overlap length, patch thickness, patch stacking sequence, adhesive thickness, parent plate thickness, etc [4, 5]. Herein finite element analysis has been shown to be essential for design and simulation. The results obtained showed that each parameter can influence more or less repair performance. But the question concerning how to find the optimal combination of these parameters in a practical way does not have yet a satisfactory answer.

The aim of this work is to propose an easy design tool for optimizing the external patched repair. Firstly, only static tension load is considered. Two series of patches have been tested with varying patch in-plane stiffness and patch stacking sequences. A finite element model has been made to identify damage initiation. The correlation between numerical and experimental results leads to define a strength ratio R^* , which can be considered as the key to the optimal repair design. Finally, a dimensionless design parameter K , very easy to determine, has been proposed.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

In this study, only a repair by «hard» patches will be considered: the pre-polymerized patches are bonded directly with the composite structure and an adhesive has to be used.

The parent plate to be repaired is a quasi-isotropic laminate in carbon/epoxy (*T600S/R368-1*) with stacking sequence: $[45/-45/0/90]_S$. The repair patches use the same prepreg with a different stacking sequence. The adhesive for bonding the patches is a structural epoxy (*PERMABOND ESP 110*). The configuration of the tested repair system is illustrated in Figure 1. A circular hole of 10 mm in diameter was drilled at the centre of the specimens to simulate the result of clearance of a damaged region, and then composite patches were bonded symmetrically on each side of the specimens. Tabs in glass/epoxy of $50 \times 50 \times 2.5$ mm are applied to the ends of the specimen.

All specimens are loaded in tension at a rate of 0.5 mm/min and at room temperature until failure. Each experimental result is an average of at least 5 specimens.

Two series of specimens were tested. The specimens in series I were designed so as to vary the in-plane stiffness of the patches and those in series II use the patches having the same in-plane stiffness but a different stacking sequence.

Figure 1: Configuration of the patched specimen tested

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Figure 2: Meshing model: (a) half specimen; (b) four possible critical zones

In order to understand effect of local stresses in the repaired system on static strength, a three dimensional finite element analysis was performed by using MSC.Patran software associated with Marc 2005 solver. A previous study [6] has showed that this software is suitable for the mechanical analysis of composite laminates. Because of the symmetry,

only one half of a patched specimen is considered in the finite element modelling (Fig. 2-a). The boundary conditions are simulated by fixing one extremity and applying a constant displacement to the other extremity in the longitudinal direction. The bonded joint is simulated as an isotropic adhesive with elastic-perfectly plastic behaviour. The patches and the parent plate are meshed layer by layer using composite elements with the real stacking sequences; elastic behaviour for the composite is assumed. The convergence test has been carried out in order to determine the number of elements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Failure process

First of all, the damage mechanisms of the specimens repaired by bonding the external patches of reference, whose stacking sequence is one half of that of the parent plate: [90/0/-45/45], need to be described. Some experimental methods such as visual observation, infrared thermograph and strain gauges are used in order to know what the real failure process is. Finite element results have been compared with the experimental observations so as to understand the damage mechanism. A parent plate fracture model has been proposed to describe the failure process as following: firstly damage initiated in the layer of the parent plate adjacent to the adhesive near the longitudinal patch edges (zone A defined in Fig. 2); and then as the damage grows, the patches and parent plate were partly or completely detached; finally, the parent plate was broken apart along the transverse direction through the holes, leaving the patches undamaged. As a conclusion, the performance of the repair depends strongly on the stress distribution and on the damage initiation in the parent plate.

Optimization method

In order to predict the damage initiation and the final failure of a repaired system, a finite element analysis has proved very useful. The adhesive properties, considered as elastic-perfectly plastic with yielding stress of 40 MPa and thickness of 0.2 mm, play an important role in the performance of the patched specimen. The failure of the adhesive can be predicted by a critical plastic strain [3]. For composite laminates with elastic behaviour, Hoffman's criterion has been used to predict the damage initiation. The strength ratio R will be used to discuss the performance of the repair, which is defined by the following equation:

$$R = C_1(\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + C_2(\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2 + C_3(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + C_4\sigma_1 + C_5\sigma_2 + C_6\sigma_3 + C_7\sigma_{23}^2 + C_8\sigma_{13}^2 + C_9\sigma_{12}^2 \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$\text{Where: } C_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{Z_t Z_c} + \frac{1}{Y_t Y_c} - \frac{1}{X_t X_c} \right) \quad C_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{X_t X_c} + \frac{1}{Z_t Z_c} - \frac{1}{Y_t Y_c} \right) \quad C_3 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{X_t X_c} + \frac{1}{Y_t Y_c} - \frac{1}{Z_t Z_c} \right)$$

$$C_4 = \frac{1}{X_t} - \frac{1}{X_c} \quad C_5 = \frac{1}{Y_t} - \frac{1}{Y_c} \quad C_6 = \frac{1}{Z_t} - \frac{1}{Z_c}$$

$$C_7 = \frac{1}{S_{23}^2} \quad C_8 = \frac{1}{S_{13}^2} \quad C_9 = \frac{1}{S_{12}^2}$$

If $|R| \geq 1$, damage will occur in composite structures

The calculation by finite element modelling on the system repaired by the reference patches is realized by applying a uniform displacement of 0.5 mm (1 mm for the whole specimen) at one end of the specimen as so to assure elastic behaviour of the composite used. Numerically, the maximum value of R in the layers of the patch is much lower than those in the parent plate, and the most critical layer is located at the first layer, which is adjacent to the bonded joint. Moreover, at this load level, the maximum plastic strain in the adhesive joint is just under 10% of the critical value, while the maximal R in the parent plate, defined as R_{max} , already attains 85%. Therefore fracture initiation in the repaired system could occur in the parent plate as soon as R_{max} attains unity. This conclusion is in good concordance with experimental observation. Moreover, if the repair parameters change, the variation of the measured failure load shows a tendency similar to that of calculated damage initiation (Fig. 4). Therefore, the optimization of the repair system can be based on damage initiation predicted by finite element analysis. For the purpose of optimization of the patch repaired system, it is necessary to harmonize each parameter of the repaired system as so to obtain an even R distribution and decrease the value of R_{max} . In general, four possible critical zones can be defined in the parent plate of the repaired system according to the results obtained by finite element calculation (Fig. 2-b), so the optimization can be realized by varying different parameters to balance the maximal strength ratio R in these zones.

Effect of patch in-plane stiffness

In order to investigate the effect of the in-plane stiffness of a patch, the specimens in series I are designed so as to vary the normalized in-plane stiffness A_{11}^* of the patches over a large range (Table 1), where A_{11} and h are respectively the in-plane stiffness of the patches in the loading direction and the thickness of applied patches. Note that the fibre angle of the adjacent ply to the adhesive joint in this series also varies.

Figure 3 presents the variation of R -zone A, R -zone B, R -zone C and R -zone D, which define respectively the maximum strength ratio R in four possible critical zones in the parent plate (Fig.2-b). It is interesting to note that zones A and C are more loaded. As the patch in-plane stiffness increases, the former decreases while the latter increases. The point of their intersection should give the optimal design. The value of the strength ratio at this point: R -zone A = R -zone C, is defined as R^* in the following part.

Table 1: Patches studied in series I

No.	Stacking sequences*	$A_{11}^*=A_{11}/h$ (GPa)
I - 1	[45/-45] _s	11.4
I - 2	[90/0/-45/45]	39.2
I - 3	[0] ₄	103.0

* The first layer is in contact with the adhesive

In addition, the experimental results provide some evidence of this. The measured ultimate failure load normalized by that of unnotched specimen has shown a decrease

with the increase of the patch in-plane stiffness (Fig. 4). The best performance is really those repaired by the [45/-45]s patches, whose in-plane stiffness is very near to the optimal point and an almost 90% strength recovery is here achieved. The prediction of the damage initiation obtained by the finite element model is also presented in Figure 4, and the variation of the ultimate failure load follows the same tendency as that of the load at damage initiation.

Numerically, the location of damage initiation for the specimens repaired by the [45/-45]s patches should be in the zone C, while that for the specimens repaired by the others patches will be in zone A (Fig. 3). In reality, their fracture surfaces are quite different. For the patches [45/-45]s, the initiation of fracture occurred clearly in the section weakened by the hole that contains the zone C (Fig. 5-a); while for the others, many more broken fibres stuck on the adhesive are observed, and the delamination appears more developed before final specimen rupture (Fig. 5-b). It suggests that damage started from zone A and then spread up to final failure of the repaired structure.

Fig. 3: Maximal strength ratio R in zones A, B, C and D as a function of A_{11}^* in the load direction of the patches studied in series I

Fig. 4: Normalized failure load measured on the specimens repaired by «hard» patches in series I and the prediction of the damage initiation by finite element analysis

Fig. 5: Failure in the specimens repaired by different patches

Effect of patch stacking sequences

The specimens studied in series II are repaired by the patches having the same normalized in-plane stiffness. The fibre orientation of the adjacent ply to the adhesive can be changed by the stacking sequence of the patch (Table 2).

Table 2: Patches studied in series II

No.	Stacking sequences*	$A_{11}^* = A_{11}/h$ (GPa)
II - 1 (I - 2)	[90/0/-45/45]	39.2
II - 2	[45/-45/90/0]	39.2
II - 3	[0/90/45/-45]	39.2

* The first layer is in contact with the adhesive

Fig. 6: Normalized failure load and damage initiation prediction obtained for the specimens repaired by the patches in series II

According to finite element modelling, R_{max} is always located at zone A whatever the stacking sequence of patches. Moreover, although the difference in the value of R_{max}

between the specimens repaired by the patches in series II is not very important, the failure loads measured on the specimens seem to confirm the prediction of damage initiation by finite element analysis: the best fibre orientation in the ply in contact with the adhesive should be 0° (Fig. 6). But the effect of fibre orientation on the performance of the patch repaired system is considered too small to be taken into account for the optimization purpose.

Effect of other parameters

- Young's modulus of adhesive: E_a

The effect of Young's modulus of adhesive, E_a , on the performance of a patched repair is studied by varying E_a from 0.5 to 3.0 GPa. The results in Figure 7 indicate that R-zone A and R-zone C depend on the Young's modulus of adhesive. For the same in-plane stiffness of patches, if the value of E_a rises, R-zone A increases, while that in the zone C decreases. The optimal in-plane stiffness of patches corresponding to the value of R^* become higher with increasing of E_a , at the same time an increase of about 14% of the value of R^* was observed when E_a varies from 0.5 to 2.0 GPa. However, only a slight decrease of R^* is noted if E_a varies from 2.0 to 3.0 GPa. Therefore, the choice of adhesive depends on the patch in-plane stiffness, and in the case of the best combination of E_a and A_{11}^* , the reduction of R^* would be limited to a value close to 0.6.

Fig. 7: The maximum value of R in zones A and C vs. A_{11}^* and E_a

- Adhesive thickness: t_a

In practice, the variation of the adhesive thickness is confined to the range between 0.05 and 0.4 mm. As shown in Figure 8, R-zone C is not at all sensitive to the variation of t_a , however R-zone A decreases significantly with increase of adhesive thickness. It means that if we use an optimal patch, thicker adhesive layer gives better performance of the repaired system. In reality, too high adhesive thickness could lead to cohesive fracture in the bonded joint. In this case, our prediction based on the parent plate fracture model would no longer be valid.

Fig. 8: The maximum value of R in zones A and C vs. A_{11}^* and t_a

- Patch thickness: t_p

If we want to keep the same A_{11}^* , the thickness of patches can be doubled or tripled just by repeating two or three times each ply. For example, in the case of the patch having the stacking sequence: $[90/0/-45/45]$, the calculation is performed on the specimens repaired by the patches with stacking sequence $[90/0/-45/45]$, $[90_2/0_2/-45_2/45_2]$, $[90_3/0_3/-45_3/45_3]$, so the thickness of these patches are respectively 0.8, 1.6 and 2.4 mm. Figure 9 presents the evolution of R-zone A and R-zone C as a function of A_{11}^* and t_p . It is shown that for the same in-plane patch stiffness, as the patch thickness increases, R-zone A increases, while R-zone C decreases. It results in an increase of optimal in-plane stiffness of patches and a reduction of the value of R^* . So using a thin patch could make the repaired system stronger.

Fig. 9: The maximum value of R in zones A and C vs. A_{11}^* and t_p

Design parameter K

In order to understand the interaction between the different parameters of a patched repair, the present results are compared in Figure 10. It is concluded that to resist the

parent plate fracture, the best patch should use a less stiff adhesive, a reasonably thick adhesive layer and a thin patch with optimal stiffness. The relationship between these parameters looks complicated. In reality, for a real repair on composite structures, some specific requirements have to be considered, such as adhesive properties, patch and bonded joint geometry, etc. So the repair parameters can be chosen in a limited range because of practical reasons. If some parameters are already selected, we need to know how to optimize other parameters.

For the purpose of design, we propose a dimensionless parameter K, which will be able not only to integrate the effect of different repair parameters in a simple manner, but also to be determined easily. Equation 2 is proposed according to the results obtained by finite element analyses and experimental tests.

$$K = \alpha \left(\frac{E_a t_p}{t_a E_p} \right)^{1/4} \frac{E_p t_p}{E_{pp} t_{pp}} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Where:

- E_a and t_a are Young's modulus and thickness of the adhesive;
- E_p and t_p are Young's modulus in loading direction and patch thickness;
- E_{pp} and t_{pp} are Young's modulus in loading direction and parent plate thickness;
- α is a repaired structure coefficient. It has to be determined empirically. In our system, $\alpha \approx 6.12$ is evaluated.

The use of this parameter supposes that if

$K = 0$, no repair ($R\text{-zone } C \gg R\text{-zone } A$); $0 < K < 1$, insufficient repair ($R\text{-zone } C > R\text{-zone } A$)

$K = 1$, optimal repair ($R\text{-zone } C = R\text{-zone } A$); $K > 1$, excessive repair ($R\text{-zone } C < R\text{-zone } A$)

If we translate the results presented in Figure 7 in terms of design parameter K. Then we can see that all of the optimal strength ratios R^* are located around $K=1.0$ and the deviation is only 3% (Fig. 11). It is obviously the validation of this design parameter K has to be confirmed by many more experimental results.

CONCLUSIONS

In the repair by bonding external patches, the final failure in tension results from the damage initiation in the parent plate at the longitudinal edges of circular patches (zone A) or at the transversal edges of hole(zone C). The location of damage initiation, as well as the process of damage evolution in the parent plate depends on the patch configuration. The key of repair optimization is to balance the stress distribution in these two zones. If the repair parameters change, the variation of the measured failure load shows a tendency similar to that of calculated damage initiation. Therefore, the optimization of the repair system can be based on the prediction of damage initiation by finite element analysis.

An optimal strength ratio R^* has been defined in this work which can be considered as the most important parameter in the repair optimization. All repair parameters may be selected in order to minimize this parameter R^* .

The effects of several parameters on the performance of the repairs, such as Young's modulus and the thickness of adhesive, the stiffness and the thickness of patch, can be integrated into a dimensionless design parameter K.

Fig. 10: Variation of R* vs. different parameters

Fig. 11: K vs. adhesive Young's modulus

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